

AN ACADEMIC GUIDE TO RESEARCH AND WRITING SKILLS IN YORÙBÁ LANGUAGE

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Abstract : This paper examines research and writing skills in Yorùbá language. It is aimed at encouraging learners of Yorùbá and explores writing skills in the language. It is designed to show case writing as one of the major language learning skills and prepare learners of the language in the prospect of undertaking a research work in Yorùbá language. Some of the main issues discussed are practical approach to research and writing that will promote the teaching and learning of the Yorùbá language at various levels. Suggestions are made on how teachers can help learners to accomplish their intentions at various levels of learning. The paper concludes that a complementary approach will be required for both product and process oriented research as well as writing skills.

Key Words: Research skill, Writing skill, Yorùbá language, Complementary approach

Introduction

Effective communication is a prerequisite for success at school and colleges and later in a job. Fortunately, good writing and speaking abilities are skills that everyone can learn through continuous practice. Moreover, learning these skills and using them can be fun.

Written communication is more formal in style than spoken communication because the message must be passed across in words alone. Effective writing requires knowledge of grammar and the ability to use words skilfully. A written message can neither make use of any of the nonverbal aspects of communication that are naturally part of speech nor can it take advantage of the immediate feedback available when we are speaking. In that case, writing has to be complete in itself and as such more difficult than speaking.

The main concern of this paper is to guide the writer with practical tips on how to become a good researcher and a better writer in Yorùbá language. It explains how to prepare a research work and suggest a good finishing for a good report through the application of complementary approach.

Yorùbá Language as a Mother Tongue or L1

Yoruba language is one of the selected Nigerian languages considered to be the language of wider communication in the Western part of the country. It serves as a means of communication and self-expression; it also makes every transaction in terms of business, politics, religion, entertainment and education possible among the speakers. As an effective medium of communication, it is important that any writing done meets the various requirements.

The Development of Yorùbá Language Writing

The effort to write in Yorùbá language started with a man called Bowdich in (1817). He printed a book titled "Mission to Ashante" in (1819). Next to him is a woman by name Hannah Kilham, who also attempted a writing about this same period. She produced some writings in Yorùbá in (1828) in a book titled "Specimen of African languages spoken in the colonies of Sierra Leone". The third person is Clapperton, who published a collection of some words in Yorùbá language in (1829). He is a missionary and a researcher. The fourth man was John Rabban. In his

own case, he went beyond the gathering of few words in Yorùbá, rather he had three different books which were published in the years (1830), (1831) and (1832) respectively.

The fifth person in the group was Edwin Norris who wrote a book titled "Outline of a vocabulary of the principal languages of Western and Central African". The was compiled and published for the use of Niger expedition in (1831). In the book, he pointed out some attestable vowel sounds and consonant sounds in the Yorùbá language such as (a e i o u, ai, au) and (g, j, ng, ch and hh). Henry Townsend and Golmer were the sixth and seventh people who in (1840) determined to get the English bible translated into Yorùbá bible. The link between these two missionaries and Samuel Ajayi Crowther gave birth to the Yorùbá bible. The effort of Bowel in (1858) cannot be left out. In a book titled "Grammar and Dictionary of the Yorùbá language" a couple of the Yorùbá orthography was produced.

However, in (1875), a meeting was summoned by the CMS in Lagos to resolve the differences in the orthography and other aspects of the Yorùbá language that needs a consensus agreement. Since then a lot of review has been carried out by professionals like "Egbé Akómólédè àti Àsà Yorùbá", the journalists, the government at the state and federal level and every concerned learners and lovers of the language in the process of writing Yorubá language in the modern day till date.

Research: Its Concept

Research has been defined in a number of different ways. In the broadest sense, research includes investigation, experimentation, testing, exploration, examination and scrutiny of any data, information, and fact-findings for the advancement of knowledge (Ajibade, 2003). Research is a process of steps used to collect and analyse information to increase our understanding of topical issues. It consists of three steps: pose a question, collect data to answer the question, and present an answer to the question (Fisher et. al., 2013). Also, research comprises creative work undertaken on a systematic basis in order to increase the stock of knowledge, and the use of this stock of knowledge to devise new applications (Panneerselvam, 2013). Research can summarily be defined as the systematic investigation into and

study of materials and sources in order to establish facts and reach conclusions. In other words, to conduct research implies that there should be orderliness and procedure in terms of gathering, organising, analysing and interpreting data.

The basic characteristics of a research work include the following: It is generated by a specific research question, hypothesis or problem; it follows a specific plan or procedure; it aims at increasing understanding by interpreting facts and reaching conclusions; it requires reasoned argument to support conclusions and it is based on previous knowledge which it aims to advance, but may also develop further questions calling for further research (Ajibade, 2017). Ajibade expresses further the purpose of a research among which are; to investigate and provide solutions to new or existing problems, to establish or confirm facts, reaffirm the results of previous work, to expand on past work in the field, to explore and analyse more general issues, to construct or create new procedures or system, to explain new phenomenon and to generate new knowledge.

There are different types of research depending on the purpose, the data collected, and how such data are analysed. There is the descriptive research which describes a particular phenomenon, focussing on the issue of what is happening, or how much of it has happened rather than why is it happening. There is exploratory research which takes place where there is little or no prior knowledge of a phenomenon, while explanatory research involves explaining why something happens and predictive research forecasts future phenomena, based on the interpretation suggested by explanatory research (Saliu and Fayeye (2007). Other categories of research are primary and secondary researches. The primary research involves collection of original data and the secondary involves the use of existing sources of data.

Research Process

According to Ajibade (2017), a research work involves a systematic process that focuses on being objective and gathering a multitude of information for analysis so that the researcher can come to a conclusion. Generally, carrying out a research involves the following stages; selection of topic, literature review, development of theoretical and conceptual framework, clarification of the

research question, gathering of data, data analysis and interpretation, discussion of the findings and drawing conclusions, references and abstract. The abstract section summarizes the papers; stating the topic, the sub topics reviewed, the methodology and the mode of analysis (if the paper is data based). It also mentions the findings and the conclusion. The introduction comprises of the general information about the background of the research work, viewing the problem to be confronted from a general perspective through a specific position. It may also include the scope of the paper, justification for the paper and its significance.

The literature review section gives general information about the background of the study. It provides the theoretical foundation and support for the research work. Subtopics that are related to the main topic must evolve from variables in the main topic. Such subtopics should be addressed with supporting views, opinions, insights and observations from scholars, authors, journal, magazines and newspapers. Such views are not meant to be merely copied down verbatim; rather ideas related to the paper's topic should be gleaned and paraphrased for use.

The methodology section gives a direction to follow in a step- by-step explanation of the process of data collection (if any) and data analysis (if any). It should also mention the ways of analysing data collected. Finding evolve from the results of the analysis are then discussed before a conclusion is drawn, with recommendation made where necessary. The last section, the reference, contains the record and details of the works cited and quoted. In some situations, bibliography is used and this refers to all works used, though not directly cited and quoted. Above all, there is the need for a research proposal as it is the summary of the research to be conducted (Ayodabo, 2008).

Writing Process

Writing is the ability to express one's self on paper by a reason of discussion, explanation, description and so on. It centres around a subject matter which must be identified by the writer. The writer is left with the responsibility of expressing his or her thoughts in words, phrases, sentences and idiomatic expressions (Oyeyemi, 2006). To Oyinkan (2005), writing is considered to be the most difficult, tasking and demanding of the language skills as the process calls for the writer's

presence of mind simultaneously with thinking, organising and writing. This means that writer reads as he writes. In fact, a good writer is recognized to be one who is able to synthesise all major activities involved in effective writings.

Preparing to Write the First Draft for a Research Work

The composition of a research study is normally carried out in three stages: writing the first draft, preparing the revision and proofreading the finished study. Each stage need to be carried out at a single setting (Moses, 2004). After choosing the topic to work on, the next thing is to read extensively and intensively before getting started. It is with a rich knowledge that a good researcher can draw an outline on how to work perfectly on the study. Among the key research sources for a good research work are the library, interviewing people, conducting a survey, using electronic media, visiting museums, art galleries, cultural centres and historical places or societies.

A good research work must be logically structured in such a way that it conducts the reader with a convincing arrangement of points to be followed easily. It should be well organised exhibiting an easy flow of ideas. The first draft of every research work is the beginning of creativity where the researcher must not lose focus of the study; neither must he allow the quantity or quality of information obtained at the stage of investigation to hijack the focus and design of the study. A researcher is not expected to recopy what he has read directly from other sources rather he should present a literature review by injecting his own idea into the work with a lot of paraphrase. It is only where particular author has said something in a very unique way that he may have to quote directly. A researcher is expected to use other people's ideas as reference or base to reinforce his own position (Ayodabo, 2008).

Furthermore, a quotation that is five or more lines long is set apart from the text, as a block quotation; that is, by extra indention at the left and by single spacing. Block quotations are not enclosed in quotation marks, because the distinctive setup shows that they are quotations. A block quotation is often introduced by a colon. A researcher should always identify his subtitles clearly and address the study clearly. He should avoid the inclusion of unrelated views under each

subtitle rather only related ideas need be put together under a particular subtitle. As he integrates the ideas together from different sources. The researcher should always remember the correct names, the sources, years of publication and pages. At the end of the draft, he need to re-read and ensure that the sentences communicate and address the topic and subtopics (Ayodabo, 2008).

A researcher must make sure that all the problems and issues raised are solved and addressed, with illustrations and justification where necessary. While revising the first draft, a writer should look for parts that are unsatisfactory and trying to improve them; such as aspect of diction that include vagueness, rubbish, jargon and triteness. A good, simple and clear diction is the choice of words that best allows a researcher to communicate his or her intentions well and appropriate to capture and hold the readers' interest. A paragraph usually consists of two or more sentences. The sentences should follow each other for coherence and avoid verbosity and ambiguity. The researcher/writer should choose words that are accurate, clear and free from bias and explain the technical words and scientific terms because a study is meant to be present. Paragraphs should be linked together so that the report becomes a logical and persuasive whole and the content of idea must flow naturally from beginning to the end. He or she should avoid the run together of two or more independent clauses and their separation with a comma as shown in the examples below:

- i. Ọlọpàá mú Adé, tì mólé (police arrested Ade, locked up)
- ii. Ọlọpàá mú Adé, Ọlọpàá ti Adé mólé (police arrested Ade, police locked Ade up)
- iii. Ọlọpàá, ti Adé mólé (police, locked Ade up)

Editing and Revising a Research Work

According to Saliu and Oyebanji (2004), easy reading is hard writing. A researcher will need to turn out a number of drafts to produce the best results. Therefore, when the work is ready, the next thing is to read, edit and revise what he or she has pencilled down carefully, keeping in mind why he is conducting the study. He or she checks if the introduction clearly state what the study is about and provide a context for what you want to present. The writer should also check the grammatical correctness of the paper and examine closely the words to know if it said what you mean or mean

what you have said. Spelling can mar the entire work, you may need to consult the dictionary and other means to keep your spellings in shape. A researcher in Yorùbá language must not forget the natural rule in Yorùbá such as: no double consonant sound can stand side-by-side in the language; avoid unnecessary sound omission in any case of phonological processes; do not go back to the outdated autography, i.e.

1. The removal of vowel /i/ in some mis-spelt words such as:

old spelling	new spelling
aiye	ayé (world)
aiya	aya (chest)
eyeye	eyé (bird)
Taiye	Táyé (name)

2. The misuse of 'an' and 'on' words in Yorùbá should be written as pronounced.

3. The words that are wrongly spelt especially in the bible should be written correctly

thus:

old spelling	new spelling
okòrin	okùnrin (man)
lèhin	lẹ̀yìn (after)
obirin	obìnrin (woman)
oma	omọ (child)
lálálá	láélé (never)
iròhin	iròyìn (news)
yíò	yóó/yóò (will)
àmìn	àmì (sign)
ogbàn	ogbòn (wisdom)
Ìtan	ìtòn (thigh)
Ìtòn	Ìtan (story)
Èron	èran (meat)
Èfan	Èfòn (mosquito)
Ìjògbàn	ìjògbòn (problem)

4. Stop the use of apostrophe on abbreviated words such as:

old spelling	new spelling
si'sé	sişé (doing/working)
rán'tí	rántí (remember)
t'ójú	tójú (take care of)
kọ'rin	kòrin (sing)
kò'lé	kólé (build a house)

5. The use of an 'n' after a third person pronoun in the object position which ends with a nasal is recommended:

old spelling	new spelling
tan a	tàn án (light it)
pón ọ	pón ọn (back it)
mò ọ	mò ọn (know it)

6. To show case nasalised vowel 'an' by repeating has heard in a word thus:

old spelling	new spelling
gan a	gan-an (exact)
ọfọn ọ	òfón-ọn (mouse)

7. To stop the wrong use of the vowel sound 'on' instead of 'òun' in a third person pronoun thus:

old spelling	new spelling
on nikan ni	òun nikan ni (he is the only one)
on náà ní ọ	òun náà ní ọ (he/she is coming)

8. Mark the following sounds with long mark as shown below:

old style	new style
ọẹş/oes	oes

9. To use n/l, m/n, ọn/an as allomorph of the same phoneme where necessary:

Bím̀b̀ọ̀ (name of girl), K̀ò̀ǹk̀ọ̀ (frog), G̀ọ̀m̀b̀ọ̀ (tribal mark),
Orom̀b̀ọ̀/òroǹb̀ọ̀ (orange), Ş̀ọ̀m̀b̀ọ̀ (a type of pepper),
Ibadan (city), Ìran (tribe), Idan/Idón (miracle)
Mò ní ọ̀ (I am coming), ebi ní pa mí (I am hungry) etc.

10. To use 'n' in place of 'ng' in the subject position thus:

old spelling	new spelling
ng ò lọ	n ò lọ (I will not go)
ng ò rí wọn	n ò rí wọn (I did not see them)

11. Keeping to the modern spellings of these words:

old spelling	new spelling
nwón	wón (they)
nyín	yín (you/yours)
enyin	eyin (you)

12. Avoid the reduplication of consonant sound in words such as:

old spelling	new spelling
Òt̀t̀a	Òt̀a (a town in Lagos state)
Èb̀út̀é m̀ét̀ta	Èbuté m̀éta (a town in Lagos state)
Ìd̀d̀ó	Ìd̀ó (a town in Lagos state)
Oshogbo	Oşogbo (a town in Qşun state)
Iléshà	Ilèşà (, , , , ,)
Offa	Òfà (a town in Kwara state)
Ọ̀shun	Ọşun (a name of a state)
Ọ̀bbà	Ọbà (a king)
Ommọ	Ọmọ (child)
Ọ̀kk̀ọ̀	Ọkọ (motor)
M̀ọ̀ǹm̀ọ̀n	Màmá (mother)

13. Avoid the use of long tone on words rather write such words in full thus:

old spelling	new spelling
Ănu	àánú (mercy)
Òt̀ọ̀	òótọ̀ (truth)
nã	nàà (that)
báyĩ	báyíi (like this)
ọ̀lọ̀p̀ã	ọlópáá (police)
ẹ̀lẹ̀f̀õ	ẹlẹfòò (vegetable seller)
alãnu	alááánú (merciful)
òrun	òórun (odour)
yĩ	yíi (this)
eléyĩ	eléyíi (this one)
ẹ̀lẹ̀r̀ĩ	ẹlẹrìi (witness)
bẹ	bèè (like that)
omoyĩ	omoyíi (this child)
rẹ̀r̀ĩn	rẹrìn-ín (laugh)
àwòrẹ̀r̀ĩn	àwòrẹrìn-ín (watch and laugh)
wọ̀n pè	wọn pè é (he was called)
ó pọ̀n ọ̀n	ó pọn ọn (she back her/nim)
mo rí	mo rí i (I saw it/him/her)

14. When there is a phonological process of assimilation of names with falling and rising tone then an additional vowel must be inserted thus:

Oní + àánú to be written as alááánú (my benefactor)
gbọ + òórun to be written as gbóóòrun (perceive odour)

15. It is in order not to mark the middle tone on vowel sound in words but marking of the two other tones are compulsory.

lọ (go), pa (kill)
 wá (come), gbà (take)
 dìdè (stand up), gbálẹ̀ (sweep), bàbá
 (father)
 ògèdè (banana), ègúsí (melon), olùkò
 (teacher)
 Olómọge (young lady), ẹgbéjọdà (uniform)
 Olúróngbé (name),
 Alágàbàgebè (dubious),

16. To apply appropriate tone on syllabic nasal consonant sounds (m and n) on words to differentiate it from ordinary consonant sounds thus:

Géńdẹ̀ (strong man)
 Pańla (fish)
 Bíńbọ̀ (name)
 Gòmńbọ̀ (tribal mark)
 kòńkọ̀ (frog)
 Bẹ̀ńbẹ̀ (drum)

17. The words below should be written thus:

Wá + owó to be written as (wówó) not (wá wó).....(look for money)
 Mú + àwo to be written as (máwo) not (má wo).....(pick a plate)
 Wá + iṣẹ̀ to be written as (wáṣẹ̀) not (ó wá ṣẹ̀).....(search for job)
 Kọ + ẹ̀kọ̀ to be written as (kẹ̀kọ̀) not (o kẹ̀ kọ̀).....(schooling/learning)
 Ó wá + imọ̀ to be written as (ó wámọ̀) not (ó wá mọ̀)... (seeking for knowledge)

18. Stop the reduplication of vowels in these words.

old spelling	new spelling
omọ omi	omọ mi (my child)
Okọ omi	okọ mi (my husband)
Ilé e wa	ilé wa (my house)
Ọrẹ ẹ mi	ọrẹ mi (my friend)

19. Using elimination process when forming new words by combining verbs and nouns that are closely related Kí á máa lo àmì ìpajẹ láàárín àpapọ̀ ọ̀rọ̀-ìṣe àti ọ̀rọ̀-orúkọ tí wón jẹ̀ alómájàá báyí:

- tọ + ojú = tọjú tàbí tọ'jú iwà rẹ (watch your ways)
- rán + eti = rántí tàbí rán'tí omọ ẹni tí iwọ n ẹ (remember the child of whom you are)
- ra + aṣọ = raṣọ tàbí r'aṣọ (buy clothe)
- kọ + iwé = kọwé tàbí kọ'wé (write a book)

20. These words should not be written together as one word.

old spelling	new spelling
Ó nlo to be written as	Ó n lọ (he/she is going)
Ó nké to be written as	Ó n ké (he/she crying)

21. These words should be written as a word or together thus:

Níbo (where)
 Nílátí (have to)
 Ìbá (should have)

22. To separate these words and not be written together as one word.

ta ni	(who)
kín ni / kí ni	(what)
wí pé	(that is)
gégé bí	(for example)
ẹni tí	(one that ...)
nítórí tí	(because of)
nígba tí	(when)
nígba gbogbo	(when ever)
èwo ni	(which one)
ibi tí	(where it is)
nítórí náà	(because of that)
níwọn ìgbà tí	(in as much)
lẹyìn náà	(after that)
bí ó tilẹ̀ jẹ̀ pé	(even if it is)
èyí tí	(that one)
jẹ̀ kí	(let it)
nígba náà	(then)

23. Keep to the use of speech marks especially the linking hypen thus:

a-dáná-ìjà (war monger)
 ògbórí-ẹlẹ̀mọ̀ṣọ̀ (a brave warlord)
 onílẹ̀-gogoro (upstair)
 o-torí-àmàlà-bá-wọ̀n-gbókù-rọ̀yọ̀ (glutton)
 ògbórí-ẹfọ̀n (brave hunter)

24. The use of capital letters at the beginning of words, among phrases and sentences

where necessary such as:
 orúkọ Olórun (name of God), orúkọ ilú (town), àdúgbò (place), orúkọ ẹniyàn, ọjọ àti ọ̀ṣù (human beings, days of the weeks, months), ìbẹ̀rẹ̀ gbólóhùn/ìpínrọ̀ (sentence/paragraph), ewi (poetry) etc.

25. Don't use capital letters in-between words.
 26. If a word is loaned into the Yorùbá language, all rules must apply. For example;
- i. Yàgò fún ìsùpò ìró kónsónàntì (avoid consonant cluster)
 - ii. Ìró kónsónàntì kì í gbèyìn ọ̀rọ̀ Yorùbá (consonant sound cannot end Yorùbá words)
 - iii. Ìró àránmúpè kì í bẹ̀rẹ̀ ọ̀rọ̀ Yorùbá. (Yorùbá words do not start with nasalised sounds)
27. Strange letters should be replaced with a similar sound in the language.

Examples are:

English language	Yorùbá language
Psychology	Saikólójì
Church	Ṣọ̀ọ̀ṣì
College	Kólẹ̀jì
Mark	Máàkì
Date	Déètì
Curriculum	Kòríkúlọ̀mù
Teacher	Tíṣà
Syllabus	Sílábọ̀ṣì

Having talked about the Yorùbá orthography, the next thing is the footnotes and graphic illustrations employed. Footnotes and any graphic illustrations used should be reviewed to ensure that they are not overlooked in the revision and avoid difficulties with spacing in the final version. The main purpose of footnotes is to document sources. It shows whose ideas are drawn. This affords the readers the opportunity of checking the glossary and relevance of quotations or other information used. Bibliography is a list of all the published sources that you have used to prepare your paper. It comes at the end of the paper. It identifies your sources exactly and usually provides more information about them than the footnotes. References are arranged alphabetically; by surname of the author, or if there is no author, by the first word a title or an article. The titles of books and journals are usually presented in italic type.

Conclusion

This paper has considered the academic guide to research and writing skills in Yorùbá language. It has also explored ways by which students can prepare themselves for written work. Students have been guided on the choice of topic to

drawing an outline, researching the topic, to the body of a well-structured paper with a beginning, middle and an end. The paper stresses some important tips to good writing i.e. grammatical accuracy, avoiding spelling error, paragraphing, coherence, editing and revising. It also suggested motivation required by writer for an effective writing. It concluded that a good research is that follows the standard process and spells the entire methods from the beginning to the end. However, the adoption of the process varies from one discipline to another.

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References

- Ajibade, B. (2003). Barriers to effective communication in Bolaji, E. B; Alabi, V.A. (ED.) in the principles and the practice of communication, Ilorin: Department of English, University of Ilorin.
- Ajibade, L. T. (2003). A guideline to report writing in Geography. Ilorin: Fola Print.
- Ajibade, L. T. (2017). Research methodology. A paper presented at a seminar organised for the academic staff by the staff orientation committee of the Kwara State Polytechnic, held at adademic conference centre (Main Campus) on 27th April.
- Ajibade, M. I., Olanrewaju, R. F. (2018). An evaluation of the factors affecting writing skill in selected senior secondary school in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria. *The Gazelle Journal, A multi-disciplinary journal of the Faculty of General Studies Federal University, Dutse*, 3 (2): 101-111
- Ayodabo, J. O. (2008). Logical presentation of papers. *Skills in Tertiary English Usage*. Ilorin: Haytee Press.
- Babatunde, S.T. (1998). Reading in English for students of English as a second Language, Ibadan: African Publisher Limited.
- Fisher, J. P., Jansen, J. A., Johnson, P. C. and Mikos (2013). Guidelines for writing a research paper for publication.
- Kumar, R. (2011). *Research Methodology: A step-by-step guide for beginners*. Washington, D. C.: SAGE.
- Moses, M. (2004). *English language communicating skill for academic purpose GSP (UNIT)*, Ibadan University Press.
- Oyeyemi, S. O. (2006). Writing: quality, paragraphing and writing a full essay in Yusuf, J. C. et. Al (eds.) in *English language teaching: A communicative approach*, Ilorin: Hayte Press and Publishing Co.
- Oyinkan, M. (2005). Essentials of essay and reflect writing. In Alabi, V. A. and Babatunde, S. T. (eds.). *In basic communication skills for students of science and humanities*, Unilorin Press, University of Ilorin.
- Panneerselvam, R. (2013). *Research methodology*. Delhi: PH Learning Private Limited.
- Saliu, H. A. and Fayeye, J. O. (2007). *Further readings in research methodology*: Ilorin: Faculty of Business and Social Sciences.
- Saliu, H. A. and Oyebanji, J. O. (2004). *A guide on research proposal and report writing*. Ilorin: Faculty of Business and Social Sciences, University of Ilorin.